

CSC

ICT Solutions for
Brilliant Minds

CSC – IT Center for Science Funet Digivisio 2030

SIG-MSP meeting 23rd Mar 2023 @Zeist

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Our special expertise includes for instance research infrastructures, interoperability, and digital transformation

Business volume in 2021
67M€

One of the world's most eco-efficient datacenter in Kajaani

Non-profit state enterprise with special tasks owned by the state of Finland **70 %** and Finnish higher education institutions **30 %**

Approx.
511
employees in
2021

CSC's history

Finland lives on diverse expertise.

In the Digivisio 2030 programme, all Finnish higher education institutions are building a future of learning together. The goal is a new era of learning where each of us can learn more easily and flexibly, thus accumulating the expertise needed in a constantly changing world.

- <https://digivisio2030.fi/en/>

DIGIVISIO 2030 – a joint programme

- Involving all Finnish higher education institutions, Digivisio 2030 is **a joint programme** whose aim is **to create a future for learning** that benefits higher education institutions, learners and our society as a whole. All 38 Finnish higher education institutions have signed the programme's participation agreement, and the programme office was established at the end of 2020.

DIGIVISIO 2030 TIMELINE

2021

All higher education institutions sign the programme's participation agreement and the Digivisio programme office is established.

2023

The first versions of the services are being piloted. Joint criteria for high quality e-learning is applied in the open offering at higher education institutions.

2022

The implementation of the services will begin, the higher education institutions will begin their change work and the vision work on e-learning will be completed.

2024

Education offering for continuous learning at higher education institutions and the learner's own data can be found in one service, which is open to all continuous learners.

DIGIVISIO 2030

- Digivisio enables **learners** to learn more easily and flexibly, thus allowing them to accumulate the necessary expertise for a constantly changing world.
- Digivisio strengthens the role of the **teacher** as a producer of high-quality content and as a facilitator of internationally renowned study experiences.
- Digivisio ensures that the standard of **higher education** rises and Finns' access to employment improves – both in Finland and abroad.

DIGIVISO 2030 aims to produce the following

1. National digital service platform
2. Guidance based on digital pedagogy, the learner's path and shared data
3. Support for change management at higher education institutions

DIGIVISO 2030 aims to produce the following

1) **National digital service platform** that

- enables **the compatibility of digital services** between higher education institutions
- provides **the learner's 'My Data' service** and integrates the learner's learning and career path with the competence accumulated before and after attending a higher education institution
- improves **the compatibility of actors' information management** and lowers the threshold for utilising national solutions.

DIGIVISO 2030 aims to produce the following

2) Guidance based on digital pedagogy, the learner's path and shared data, that

- **supports studies** and students' well-being **regardless of time and place** and in an accessible manner,
- establishes **artificial intelligence solutions** as a guidance tool and
- puts **the learner's benefit at the centre** of development.

DIGIVISO 2030 aims to produce the following

- 3) Support for change management at higher education institutions, so that we will be able to
- **deploy** the national digital service platform,
 - **digitalise study administration processes** and applying to higher education institutions
 - **support the evolution of higher education institutions** into open communities with knowledge-based management
 - **give** individuals and society **access to data**.

DIGIVISO 2030 - STEERING

- The steering and decision-making models of the Digiviso 2030 programme have been built in accordance with the principles of transparency and openness.
- **The General Assembly**, composed of representatives from all higher education institutions, is the supreme decision-maker of the programme.
- **The steering group** steers the operational activities of the programme in accordance with the guidelines of the General Assembly. The higher education institutions have elected representatives to serve in the programme steering group.

DIGIVISO 2030 - STEERING

- **The programme office** is responsible for the practical implementation of the programme. Practical development work is guided by the objectives and roadmaps established with the higher education institutions, i.e. the General Assembly and the steering group.
- **The management groups** provide operational support to the internal projects within the framework of the project plan. The steering group appoints the management groups.

Digivisio management model and organisational structure

DIGIVISIO 2030 – Funding and Legislative aspects

- Digivisio 2030 is an ambitious and long-term programme. Its funding involves the use of multiple sources of funding to achieve the programme objective.
 - In 2021, the Ministry of Education and Culture awarded a special grant of EUR 20 million to the Digivisio 2030 programme.
 - In addition to the special grant, the Ministry of Education and Culture has allocated EUR 17.8 million in strategic funding to the programme for 2021-2024.
 - As part of Finland's Sustainable Growth Programme, the programme has been granted an additional EUR 6 million until 2024.
- With regard to legislation, the Digivisio 2030 programme works in close cooperation with the Ministry of Education and Culture. One of the priorities of the programme is to identify possible needs for changes in legislation so that Digivisio can be realized.

DIGIVISIO 2030 – output of the Study on possible legislative obstacles (late Y2020)

1. The need for a thorough definition and concrete approach: What is the learner's personal data, how is it generated and what is it used for? The need to amend the statutes and the higher education institutions' own regulations cannot otherwise be identified
2. Another main observation is the satisfactory handling of data protection and information security issues from the start of the project.
3. Digivisio was seen as driving the higher education field to think more deeply about the role of the right to a degree in 2030
4. **The learning ecosystem that Digivisio aims to achieve will not be created without changes in laws and regulations.**

DIGIVISIO 2030 – Learners and high-quality pedagogy

- The target group of Digivisio is exceptionally broad. The aim is that, in the future, all learners can use Digivisio services regardless of their prior competence, level of education or labour market status.
- Development work is carried out in close cooperation with learners. The programme drafted a report on its different user groups, and the user forum is actively used in the development of services and operating models.
- The growing importance of digital pedagogy and support for well-being in the learning process requires new kinds of skills from teachers, tutors and education planners. Digivisio also seeks solutions and tools for developing digital pedagogy.

DIGIVISIO 2030 – Needs for the Success

- The success of Digivisio requires extensive expertise from the entire field of higher education. The staff of higher education institutions play a key role in defining and coordinating the processes, concepts and operating methods enabling Digivisio.
- The services produced in the Digivisio programme will be developed in close cooperation with higher education institutions through piloting.
- The programme will also focus on support for change management in higher education institutions. The programme for support for change management is being prepared in cooperation with higher education institutions

DIGIVISIO 2030 – the Aim

- The aim of Digivisio is to create an open, recognized learning ecosystem based on Digivisio's digital services, the joint study offering of higher education institutions and interaction with companies and society.
- The aim is to ensure long-term development and create the preconditions for future service development. Solutions are created openly in order to integrate them with other existing services and interfaces.
- Studies related to the ecosystem are currently being conducted, with the aim being to launch the first pilots in 2024.

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A problem has been detected and Windows has been shut down to prevent damage to your computer.

UNMOUNTABLE_BOOT_VOLUME

If this is the first time you've seen this error screen, restart your computer. If this screen appears again, follow these steps:

Check to make sure any new hardware or software is properly installed. If this is a new installation, ask your hardware or software manufacturer for any Windows updates you might need.

If problems continue, disable or remove any newly installed hardware or software. Disable BIOS memory options such as caching or shadowing. If you need to use Safe Mode to remove or disable components, restart your computer, press F8 to select Advanced Startup Options, and then select Safe Mode.

Technical Information:

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